

The influence of tourist satisfaction on revisit intention: the moderating role of health consciousness

Suliyanto, Rahab, Destia Vindha Arini

Department of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Jenderal Soedirman University, Purwokerto, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Cleanliness, health, safety, and environment sustainability (CHSE) certification is an indicator of a COVID-19-safe tourist destination. Baturraden tourist destination has received a CHSE level certificate very good but the effect is not yet known on tourist satisfaction and intention to visit again. This study aimed to analyze the effect of the element CHSE on revisit intention through tourist satisfaction and health consciousness as a moderating variable. This research is survey research by collecting data from 149 respondents who had visited the Baturraden tourist destination. Five Likert scale is used to measure research construct. To test the causal relationship between constructs, structural equation modelling (SEM) with SmartPLS is used. The findings of this research are cleanliness, environmental sustainability, health, and safety have a positive effect on tourist satisfaction, and tourist satisfaction has a positive effect on revisit intention, but health consciousness and the moderating effect of health consciousness have no effect on revisit intention.

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Corresponding Author:

Suliyanto

Department of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business, Jenderal Soedirman University

Purwokerto, Indonesia

Email: suliyanto@unsoed.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

Tourism plays an important role in the economic, social, and cultural development of many countries. According to the World Tourism Barometer report [1], the global tourism industry has contributed nearly US\$1.5 trillion in tourism spending and recorded 1.5 billion tourist arrivals in 2019. In this regard, tourism provides significant economic benefits such as increased tax revenues, job creation, and local economic diversification [2], [3]. This indicates that tourism's potential impact on a country's economy that can manage its destinations well may become increasingly important in the future.

However, the COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on various sectors. The COVID-19 pandemic crisis has had an unprecedented impact on the tourism industry, causing the closure of international borders around the world, flight bans for airplanes and other modes of transportation, as well as forced repatriation of tourists, and lockdowns of residents to remain at home in various parts of the world. In 2019-2020 [4], [5]. International tourist arrivals are predicted to decline by up to 78%, with revenue losses of around US\$ 1.2 trillion, as well as job losses of around 120 million people which is the biggest decline in this era [1]. The COVID-19 pandemic has had an impact on the tourism sector worldwide, including the country of Indonesia since March 2020. It is clear that COVID-19 has reduced the number of visitors in the tourism sector, which has had a major impact on the overall tourism industry revenue [6], [7], and has changed the behavior of tourists [8]. The impact of the crisis is expanding for tourism as it creates socio-cultural and geo-strategic tensions, with increasing anti-China rhetoric and racism based on perceptions of China as the origin and spread of the virus [9].

The COVID-19 pandemic is an infectious disease that has emerged in a new era [10]. People's perceptions of disease when they encounter an infectious disease, such as the way it spreads, the death rate, the number of cases affected, and symptoms of fever, can influence tourists' decisions in choosing to visit a destination [11]. This makes tourists more health conscious. Research Pu *et al.* [12], stated that the COVID-19 pandemic has increased tourists' awareness of the importance of health, especially when they are planning a trip during the COVID-19 pandemic. It is important for an entity to be able to understand customer conditions, so that it can adjust to conditions and needs [13]. Tourists are increasingly taking care of their safety and health while traveling to a destination [10].

As COVID-19 spreads around the world, international and business travel has almost completely stopped, and domestic travel has also seen a significant decline. Nonetheless, interest in tourism is still there and is likely to see a significant increase [14]. This can happen because tourism activities have the potential to have a positive impact on the health of tourists through their tourism experience. The tourism experience gives positive emotions and makes tourists carry out social interactions with residents [3], [15], [16]. Experiencing positive emotions gained through tourism activities can reduce the risk of cardiovascular disease, inflammation, headaches, weakness, and stress [17], [18]. Therefore, engaging in fun tourism activities can contribute to overall physical and mental health.

Cleanliness, health, safety, environment sustainability (CHSE) certification is the process of granting certificates to tourism businesses, tourism destinations, and other types of businesses in the tourism sector. To provide guarantees to tourists on the implementation of cleanliness, health, safety, and environmental sustainability. CHSE was set to be a guideline for the tourism and creative economy sector in Indonesia from September-October 2020, for the first time it was implemented during the COVID-19 period in the tourism sector and continued in other creative sectors [19]. Several researchers have previously conducted studies related to how factors such as safety [20], cleanliness [21], health [22], environmental sustainability [23] affect tourist satisfaction, and CHSE influences tourist interest to revisit through the influence of tourist satisfaction as a moderating variable [19]. Other research has also examined a lot about tourist satisfaction in influencing behavioral intentions in various tourist destinations around the world [24]–[35]. Tourist satisfaction is one of the main factors in assessing the feasibility and effectiveness of tourism products as a whole, including the facilities and services provided. The main goal is to create a satisfying experience for tourists so that the destination can compete well in the tourism industry [36]. In the travel and tourism literature, the relationship between satisfaction and intention to return has been widely discussed. However, it is still rare to pay attention to the moderating role of perceived health risk in the relationship between tourist satisfaction and intention to return.

Baturraden tourist destination is a natural tourist destination in Banyumas Regency-Central Java, Indonesia which is well known by both domestic and foreign tourists. During the COVID-19 pandemic, all Baturraden tourist destinations have implemented CHSE-based management, and have received CHSE certification from the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy in collaboration with the National Standardization Agency at a very good level. Although it has received a very good CHSE level certification, it does not have information on the effect of implementing CHSE on tourist satisfaction and its impact on revisit intention. This study aimed to analyze the effect of CHSE elements on tourist satisfaction and analyze the effect of tourist satisfaction on revisit intention with health consciousness as a moderating variable.

2. METHOD

The target population in this study is people who have visited Baturraden Destination which is located in Purwokerto, Banyumas, Central Java, Indonesia. The sample size in this study was 149 respondents who were taken randomly. Data was collected through a questionnaire distributed online. In this study, the measurement items for each construct and variable were adapted and modified from various literature to construct questionnaire statements [10], [37]–[45]. Some of the items used in this study used a Likert five scale, where a value of 1 stated strongly disagree and 5 stated strongly agreed because measuring the condition of respondents can be done with the Likert scale [46]. In this study, the Partial Least Square (PLS) bootstrapping technique was used to examine the relationship between constructs [47]. After that, an analysis and interpretation of the PLS model was carried out through two stages, namely testing of measurement and testing of the structural model [48]. Loading factor and average variance extracted (AVE) are used to test the internal validity or convergent validity [49] and cross-loading is used to test discriminant validity. Cronbach's alpha is used for internal consistency tests [50], [51] and composite reliability (CR) [52].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Respondent profile

The respondent profile is an important factor in a study Rachmawati *et al.* [53], analysis of the characteristics of the respondents is needed to know the research subjects well. Table 1 presents the characteristics of respondents who are people who have visited the Baturraden Destination. This study obtained 149 respondents received from the distribution of questionnaires, of which 62% were women and 38% were men. Looking at age information, as many as 82% of respondents in this study were young people under 25 years old, followed by respondents aged 26-35 years by 12%, 36-45 years by 4%, and respondents aged less than 45 years by 2%. Based on educational qualifications, the majority of respondents in this study were high school graduates as many as 52%, then college by 46%, and the other 2% were junior high school graduates. Based on the intensity of visits to Baturraden tourist sites, the majority of respondents are not the first visit to the tourist site, 38% of visitors have traveled in Baturraden 2-4 times, then 37% of them have visited more than 4 times, while tourists who have just visited Baturraden by 25%. In general, tourist information when visiting Baturraden is information obtained from family, friends, and social media. The reason respondents visit these tourist destinations is mostly aimed at eliminating boredom, which is 69% and gaining new experiences by 21%, while the other 11% are divided into learning by 3%, health reasons by 3%, and 4% for other reasons.

3.2. Model assesment

According to Hair *et al.* [49], an indicator can be said to be valid if it has a loading factor greater than 0.50 and cross loading greater than 0.70, Cronbach's alpha greater than 0.60 and composite reliability greater than 0.70 to be said to be reliable, and average variance extract (AVE) greater than 0.50 to say good. Table 2 shows that all indicators are valid and reliable, and variable reliability is very good. To calculate the Q-Square predictive relevance or the stone-geisser Q-Square test, the goodness of fit model test is required [47]. The Q2 value is equivalent to the total coefficient of determination in the path analysis. Q-square of 0.945 is obtained. Thus, this research model can be stated to have a goodness of fit in the medium criteria because it is greater than 33% [47]. To test the causal relationship between constructs, Structural Equation Modeling with SmartPLS is used which is shown in Table 3, while pictographic test results are shown in Figure 1.

Table 1. Respondent characteristics

Respondent profile	Information	Total	Percentage
Gender	Man	57	38%
	Woman	92	62%
	Total	149	100%
Age	<25 years	122	82%
	26-35 years	18	12%
	36-45 years	6	4%
	>45 years	3	2%
	Total	149	100%
Last education	College	68	46%
	High school	78	52%
	Junior high school	3	2%
	Total	149	100%
Visit frequency	First time	37	25%
	2 to 4 times	57	38%
	More than 4 times	55	37%
	Total	149	100%
Sources of information related to destinations	Family	58	39%
	Friend	41	28%
	Social media	38	26%
	Internet	8	5%
	Electronic advertising (TV/Radio)	2	1%
	Print Ads (brochures/leaflets)	1	1%
	Other	1	1%
	Total	149	100%
Visiting orientation	To reduce boredom	103	69%
	To get new experiences	32	21%
	For health	4	3%
	For education	4	3%
	Other	6	4%
	Total	149	100%

Table 2. Result of validity and reliability test

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	Cross Loading	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Cleanliness	CL1	0.852	0.805	0.727	0.846	0.648
	CL2	0.819				
	CL3	0.740				
Environmental sustainability	ES1	0.760	0.754	0.748	0.841	0.569
	ES2	0.719				
	ES3	0.729				
	ES4	0.807				
Health	H1	0.780	0.757	0.751	0.843	0.573
	H2	0.771				
	H3	0.753				
	H4	0.721				
Health consciousness	HA1	0.847	0.794	0.853	0.895	0.631
	HA2	0.834				
	HA3	0.715				
	HA4	0.807				
	HA5	0.759				
Moderating effect of health consciousness	Tourist satisfaction	3.551	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Revisit intention	RI1	0.837	0.846	0.801	0.882	0.715
	RI2	0.782				
	RI3	0.912				
Safety	S1	0.850	0.801	0.721	0.843	0.642
	S2	0.768				
	S3	0.784				
Tourist satisfaction	TS1	0.555	0.734	0.852	0.889	0.538
	TS2	0.779				
	TS3	0.740				
	TS4	0.757				
	TS5	0.823				
	TS6	0.814				
	TS7	0.625				

Table 3. Test results of structural model

No	Independent variable	Dependent variable	Original sample (o)	T statistics	p-value	Results
1	Cleanliness	Tourist satisfaction	0.252	3.934	0.000	Significant
2	Environmental sustainability	Tourist satisfaction	0.288	3.054	0.002	Significant
3	Health	Tourist satisfaction	0.359	4.571	0.000	Significant
4	Safety	Tourist Satisfaction	0.145	2.189	0.029	Significant
5	Tourist satisfaction	Revisit intention	0.637	3.752	0.000	Significant
6	Health consciousness	Revisit intention	0.238	1.370	0.171	Not significant
7	Moderating effect of Health consciousness	Revisit Intention	0.051	1.442	0.150	Not significant

Figure 1. Result of structural equation modelling

3.2.1. Discussion

Cleanliness has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction ($p=0.000<0.05$). This is because a clean and well-maintained destination can create a comfortable and pleasant environment. This is in accordance with the results of the study [19], [54]. In Bagri's research also states that cleanliness is an important factor in evaluating satisfaction [55]. Several previous studies also stated that cleanliness has a significant effect on customer satisfaction [19], [54].

Health has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction ($p=0.000<0.05$). The concern of tourists to improve their health and quality of life is one of the motivating factors for them to travel from one place to another [56]. His research on health tourism trends, health affects tourist satisfaction [57]. Health-conscious tourists are usually active in tourism activities such as sightseeing, participating in cultural programs, visiting spas medical treatments, and the like [58]. Health plays an important and significant role in traveler satisfaction [19], [59].

Safety has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction ($p=0.029<0.05$). This is because tourists can take part in tourism activities in peace if they feel safe. One of the factors that tourists consider when visiting natural tourism is related to the safety of visitors from risks that may occur in nature. So they can focus and enjoy a destination without worrying about potential dangers. Research by Bagri and Kala [55] shows that safety is one of the factors that have a significant influence in determining tourist satisfaction [20] states that if travelers have a positive perception of safety and security, it can contribute to increasing their trip satisfaction. Some previous studies have stated that safety has a significant effect on tourist satisfaction [19], [59].

Environmental sustainability has a positive effect on tourist satisfaction ($p=0.002<0.05$). This is because tourists feel they have values that are in line with a destination that is environmentally responsible. They will feel connected when a destination can have a positive long-term impact on the environment. So they feel satisfied with the experience they enjoy because it does not harm the environment or the local community. The results of this study are following several previous studies that state that environmental sustainability has a positive effect on satisfaction [19], [60]-[62].

Tourist satisfaction influences the revisit intention ($p=0.000<0.05$). This is because tourists assume that if they are satisfied with their travel experience, they will want to return to visit the destination to repeat the experience. This is following research [19], [20], [59]. Tourist destinations that provide a satisfying experience can build visitor loyalty. These positive experiences create pleasant memories, which encourage visitors to want to repeat them. This is following the results of the study [24], [63]-[65].

Health consciousness has no significant effect on revisit intention ($p=0.0171>0.05$). Health consciousness does not have a direct effect on the intention to revisit tourist destinations. This is because revisit intention is more influenced by the positive experiences felt by tourists on previous visits, such as natural beauty, culture, tourist activities, and services, in addition to economic factors, such as transportation and accommodation costs, entrance ticket costs are the main considerations for tourists to visit again. In general, the motivation of tourists to travel is more driven by the desire to have fun, so one's health awareness is only a secondary factor to visit again. This is in line with research Park *et al.* state that health consciousness has no significant effect on traveler satisfaction [66].

Health consciousness does not moderate the relationship between tourist satisfaction and revisit intention ($p=0.150>0.05$). This shows that health awareness does not affect the extent to which tourist satisfaction can affect the intention to return. This shows that the effect of tourist satisfaction on revisit intention is not determined by travelers' health consciousness. This is not in line with the results of the study [67], [68] which suggests that health awareness can play a moderating role. Health consciousness positively moderated the relationship between traveller happiness and intention to revisit health consciousness significantly moderated the relationship between perceived stress and satisfaction [68]. This research was conducted on natural tourism destinations associated with healthy tourism which is very relevant to CHSE elements by offering natural beauty, and air coolness, so future research needs to be retested in the context of cultural tourism, religious tourism, and culinary tourism by placing demographic variables and health environment as moderation variables.

4. CONCLUSION

The results of the study prove that cleanliness, health, safety, and environmental sustainability have a positive effect on tourist satisfaction, tourist satisfaction has a positive effect on revisit intention, but health consciousness has no effect on revisit intention and also does not moderate the relationship between tourism satisfaction and revisit intention. Satisfaction plays a very important role in increasing revisit intention. Thus, companies in the tourism industry need to pay attention to and also improve cleanliness, health, safety, and environmental sustainability in tourist destinations. It is also important to develop training and certification programs such as CHSE intending to improve the quality of service, safety, and comfort of tourists. For

further research, it is necessary to carry out research that focuses on factors that influence tourist satisfaction in more depth, as well as involving larger samples from various types of tourist destinations to obtain more comprehensive knowledge regarding the influence of CHSE on tourist satisfaction and intention to return.

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REFERENCES

- [1] United Nations World Tourism Organization, "World tourism barometer," United Nations World Tourism Organization. [Online]. Available: <https://www.e-unwto.org/loi/wtobarometereng>
- [2] D. Gursoy, Z. Ouyang, R. Nunkoo, and W. Wei, "Residents' impact perceptions of and attitudes towards tourism development: a meta-analysis," *Journal of Hospitality Marketing and Management*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 306–333, 2019, doi: 10.1080/19368623.2018.1516589.
- [3] E. J. Jordan, D. M. Spencer, and G. Prayag, "Tourism impacts, emotions and stress," *Annals of Tourism Research*, vol. 75, pp. 213–226, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.annals.2019.01.011.
- [4] Elizabeth Becker, "How hard will the coronavirus hit the travel industry?," National Geographic. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/travel/2020/04/how-coronavirus-is-impacting-the-travel-industry/>
- [5] F. Higgins-Desbiolles, "The end of global travel as we know it: an opportunity for sustainable tourism," *The Conversation*, vol. 17, pp. 1–4, 2020.
- [6] S. Jhonson and P. Boone, "From lockdown to locked in, here's what post-pandemic travel could look like," World Economic Forum. Accessed: Jun. 03, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/05/coronavirus-lockdown-travel-tourism/>
- [7] United Nations World Tourism Organization, "Impact assessment of the COVID-19 outbreak on international tourism," United Nations World Tourism Organization. [Online]. Available: <https://www.unwto.org/impact-assessment-of-the-covid-19-outbreak-on-international-tourism>
- [8] J. De Vos, "The effect of COVID-19 and subsequent social distancing on travel behavior," *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, vol. 5, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.trip.2020.100121.
- [9] T. Jamal and C. Budke, "Tourism in a world with pandemics: local-global responsibility and action," *Journal of Tourism Futures*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 181–188, 2020, doi: 10.1108/JTF-02-2020-0014.
- [10] P. Pahrudin, C. T. Chen, and L. W. Liu, "A modified theory of planned behavioral: A case of tourist intention to visit a destination post pandemic Covid-19 in Indonesia," *Heliyon*, vol. 7, no. 10, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e08230.
- [11] A. Huang, C. Makridis, M. Baker, M. Medeiros, and Z. Guo, "Understanding the impact of COVID-19 intervention policies on the hospitality labor market," *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, vol. 91, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102660.
- [12] B. Pu, F. Du, L. Zhang, and Y. Qiu, "Subjective knowledge and health consciousness influences on health tourism intention after the COVID-19 pandemic: A prospective study," *Journal of Psychology in Africa*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 131–139, 2021, doi: 10.1080/14330237.2021.1903181.
- [13] Suliyanto, W. Novandari, and Suwaryo, "The influence of market orientation on marketing performances in micro small and medium-sized (MSMEs) coconut sugar enterprises: The role of innovation," *Quality - Access to Success*, vol. 20, no. 172, pp. 143–147, 2019.
- [14] H. Kamata, "Tourist destination residents' attitudes towards tourism during and after the COVID-19 pandemic," *Current Issues in Tourism*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 134–149, 2022, doi: 10.1080/13683500.2021.1881452.
- [15] M. Godovykh and A. D. A. Tasci, "Customer experience in tourism: A review of definitions, components, and measurements," *Tourism Management Perspectives*, vol. 35, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.tmp.2020.100694.
- [16] S. Filep and P. Pearce, *Tourist experience and fulfilment: Insights from positive psychology*, 1st ed. Routledge, 2013. doi: 10.4324/9780203134580.
- [17] J. K. Boehm and L. D. Kubzansky, "The heart's content: The association between positive psychological well-being and cardiovascular health," *Psychological Bulletin*, vol. 138, no. 4, pp. 655–691, 2012, doi: 10.1037/a0027448.
- [18] F. B.L., C. M.A., C. K.A., P. J., and F. S.M., "Open Hearts Build Lives: Positive Emotions, Induced Through Loving-Kindness Meditation, Build Consequential Personal Resources," *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, vol. 95, no. 5, pp. 1045–1062, 2008.
- [19] G. Sandhubaya, S. Hidayatullah, and N. Roedjinandari, "Study of influence of cleanliness, health, safety & environment sustainability on tourist to revisit the beaches of Indonesia," *International Journal of Advances in Scientific Research and Engineering*, vol. 07, no. 10, pp. 36–47, 2021, doi: 10.31695/IJASRE.2021.34090.
- [20] A. D. A. Tasci and Y. Boylu, "Cultural comparison of tourists' safety perception in relation to trip satisfaction," *International Journal of Tourism Research*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 179–192, 2010, doi: 10.1002/jtr.745.
- [21] M. C. Vos, M. Galetzka, M. P. Mobach, M. van Hagen, and A. T. H. Pruyn, "Measuring perceived cleanliness in service environments: Scale development and validation," *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, vol. 83, pp. 11–18, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2019.04.005.
- [22] M. Sarker, N. Kasem, B. K. M. Wong, and S. Moghavvemi, "Conceptualizing essential components affecting health tourism satisfaction in asia: does context matter?," *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality and Tourism*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 1107–1135, 2022, doi: 10.1080/1528008X.2021.1955237.
- [23] A. Smith and M. Pitt, "Sustainable workplaces and building user comfort and satisfaction," *Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 144–156, 2011, doi: 10.1108/14630011111170436.
- [24] J. Alegre and J. Garau, "Tourist satisfaction and dissatisfaction," *Annals of Tourism Research*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 52–73, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.annals.2009.07.001.
- [25] D. A. Baker and J. L. Crompton, "Quality, satisfaction and behavioral intentions," *Annals of Tourism Research*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 785–804, 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0160-7383(99)00108-5.

- [26] C. F. Chen and F. S. Chen, "Experience quality, perceived value, satisfaction and behavioral intentions for heritage tourists," *Tourism Management*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 29–35, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.tourman.2009.02.008.
- [27] C. G.-Q. Chi and H. Qu, "Examining the structural relationships of destination image, tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty: An integrated approach," *Tourism Management*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 624–636, Aug. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.tourman.2007.06.007.
- [28] M. F. Cracolici and P. Nijkamp, "The attractiveness and competitiveness of tourist destinations: A study of Southern Italian regions," *Tourism Management*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 336–344, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.tourman.2008.07.006.
- [29] M. Kozak, "Comparative assessment of tourist satisfaction with destinations across two nationalities," *Tourism Management*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 391–401, 2001, doi: 10.1016/S0261-5177(00)00064-9.
- [30] M. Kozak and M. Rimmington, "Tourist satisfaction with Mallorca, Spain, as an off-season holiday destination," *Journal of Travel Research*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 260–269, 2000, doi: 10.1177/004728750003800308.
- [31] C. H. Marcussen, "Determinants of tourist satisfaction and intention to return," *Tourism*, vol. 59, no. 2, pp. 203–221, 2011.
- [32] L. Osti, M. Disegna, and J. G. Brida, "Repeat visits and intentions to revisit a sporting event and its nearby destinations," *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 31–42, 2012, doi: 10.1177/1356766711428803.
- [33] A. Pizam, Y. Neumann, and A. Reichel, "Dimensions of tourist satisfaction with a destination area," *Annals of Tourism Research*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 314–322, 1978, doi: 10.1016/0160-7383(78)90115-9.
- [34] S. Wang and H. Qu, "A study of tourists' satisfaction determinants in the context of the Pearl River Delta sub-regional destinations," *Journal of Hospitality and Leisure Marketing*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 49–63, 2006, doi: 10.1300/J150v14n03_05.
- [35] Y. Yoon and M. Uysal, "An examination of the effects of motivation and satisfaction on destination loyalty: a structural model," *Tourism Management*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 45–56, Feb. 2005, doi: 10.1016/j.tourman.2003.08.016.
- [36] M. Fuchs and K. Weiermair, "New perspectives of satisfaction research in tourism destinations," *Tourism Review*, vol. 58, no. 3, pp. 6–14, 2003, doi: 10.1108/eb058411.
- [37] N. Barber and J. M. Scarcelli, "Enhancing the assessment of tangible service quality through the creation of a cleanliness measurement scale," *Managing Service Quality*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 70–88, 2010, doi: 10.1108/09604521011011630.
- [38] Seung Ah Yoo, "Customer Perceptions of Restaurant Cleanliness: A Cross Cultural Study," 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://hdl.handle.net/10919/34127>
- [39] H. Kim and J. R. Bachman, "Examining customer perceptions of restaurant restroom cleanliness and their impact on satisfaction and intent to return," *Journal of Foodservice Business Research*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 191–208, 2019, doi: 10.1080/15378020.2019.1596002.
- [40] M. F. Chen and P. J. Tung, "Developing an extended theory of planned behavior model to predict consumers' intention to visit green hotels," *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, vol. 36, pp. 221–230, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2013.09.006.
- [41] P. Pahrudin, C. Chia-Ying, L. Li-Wei, and M. Ali, "Intention to visit of local tourist to destination image after disaster: a structural equation model approach," *Talent Development & Excellence*, vol. 12, no. No.3s, pp. 2922 – 2944, 2020.
- [42] T. Fan, B. Pu, S. Powpaka, and L. Hao, "The impact of disaster of a national airline on the Nation's Tourism: An empirical investigation," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 11, no. 5, 2019, doi: 10.3390/su11051233.
- [43] H. Oh, "Service quality, customer satisfaction, and customer value: A holistic perspective," *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 67–82, 1999, doi: 10.1016/s0278-4319(98)00047-4.
- [44] A. Singh and R. Singh, "Factors affecting wildlife tourism and satisfaction of wildlife tourist in Jim Corbett National Park," *Tourism: Theory and Practice*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 50–76, 2009.
- [45] I. U. Canny, "An empirical investigation of service quality, tourist satisfaction and future behavioral intentions among domestic local tourist at Borobudur Temple," *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 86–91, 2013, doi: 10.7763/IJTEF.2013.V4.265.
- [46] A. Curatman, A. Suroso, and Suliyanto, "Loyalty program and communication effectiveness as drivers of store loyalty," *Measuring Business Excellence*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 417–432, 2022, doi: 10.1108/MBE-11-2020-0154.
- [47] W. W. Chin, "The partial least squares approach to structural equation modeling," in *Modern methods for business research*, no. April, 1998, p. 44.
- [48] J. Hulland, "Use of partial least squares (PLS) in strategic management research: a review of four recent studies," *Strategic Management Journal*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 195–204, Feb. 1999, doi: 10.1002/(SICI)1097-0266(199902)20:2<195::AID-SMJ13>3.0.CO;2-7.
- [49] J. F. Hair, W. C. Black, and B. J. Babin, *RE Anderson Multivariate data analysis: A global perspective*. New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall, 2010.
- [50] J. C. Nunnally, *Psychometric Theory*. in McGraw-Hill series in psychology. McGraw-Hill, 1978. [Online]. Available: <https://books.google.co.id/books?id=WE59AAAAMAAJ>
- [51] L. J. Cronbach, "Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests," *Psychometrika*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 297–334, 1951, doi: 10.1007/BF02310555.
- [52] D. F. Fornell, C., & Larcker, "Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error," *Journal of Marketing Research This*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 39–50, 2016.
- [53] E. Rachmawati, Suliyanto, and A. Suroso, "Direct and indirect effect of entrepreneurial orientation, family involvement and gender on family business performance," *Journal of Family Business Management*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 214–236, 2022, doi: 10.1108/JFBM-07-2020-0064.
- [54] M. Yasami, K. Phetvaroon, and H. Zhu, "International tourists' Choices and satisfaction of small restaurants in thailand: the influence of food safety indicators," *Journal of Foodservice Business Research*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 499–532, 2022, doi: 10.1080/15378020.2021.1964340.
- [55] S. C. Bagri and D. Kala, "Tourists' satisfaction at trijuginarayan, india: an importance-performance analysis," *Advances in Hospitality and Tourism Research (AHTR) An International Journal of Akdeniz University Tourism Faculty*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 59–115, 2015.
- [56] D. Tomka, V. Holodkov, and I. Andjelković, "Quality of life as a travel motivational factors of senior tourists - Results of research in Novi Sad," *Informatologia*, vol. 48, no. 1–2, pp. 62–70, 2015.
- [57] A. Pollock, P. Williams, W. C. Gartner, and D. W. Lime, "Health tourism trends: closing the gap between health care and tourism," *Trends in outdoor recreation, leisure and tourism*, pp. 165–173, 2000.
- [58] I. Y. Yoo, T. J. Lee, and C. K. Lee, "Effect of health and wellness values on festival visit motivation," *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 152–170, 2015, doi: 10.1080/10941665.2013.866970.
- [59] Soehardi, "Model of increasing tourist satisfaction through attraction, accessibility, security, safety, health and hygiene at the Ujung Kulon National Park," *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal)*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 12155–12168, 2021.
- [60] Z. Awang, Y. Yusnita, and A. Afthanorhan, "Sustainable tourism: the moderating effect of tourists' educational background in the

- relationship between green practices and customer satisfaction,” *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, vol. 7, no. 4.34, p. 21, 2018, doi: 10.14419/ijet.v7i4.34.23574.
- [61] S. Thipsingh, W. A. Srisathan, S. Wongsachia, C. Ketkaew, P. Naruethradhol, and L. Hengboriboon, “Social and sustainable determinants of the tourist satisfaction and temporal revisit intention: A case of Yogyakarta, Indonesia,” *Cogent Social Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 1, 2022, doi: 10.1080/23311886.2022.2068269.
- [62] S. S. Jasrotia, M. K. Kamila, and V. K. Patel, “Impact of Sustainable tourism on tourist’s satisfaction: evidence from India,” *Business Perspectives and Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 173–189, 2023, doi: 10.1177/22785337211043960.
- [63] J. F. Petrick, “The roles of quality, value and satisfaction in predicting cruise passengers’ behavioral intentions,” *Journal of Travel Research*, vol. 42, no. 4, pp. 397–407, 2004, doi: 10.1177/0047287504263037.
- [64] G. Prayag, “Tourists’ evaluations of destination image, satisfaction, and future behavioral intentions—the case of mauritius,” *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, vol. 26, no. 8, pp. 836–853, Dec. 2009, doi: 10.1080/10548400903358729.
- [65] B. N. Rittichainuwat, H. Qu, and C. Mongkonvanit, “A study of the impact of travel satisfaction on the likelihood of travelers to revisit thailand,” *Journal of Travel and Tourism Marketing*, vol. 12, no. 2–3, pp. 19–43, 2015, doi: 10.1300/J073v12n02_03.
- [66] J. K. Park, J. Ahn, and W. S. Yoo, “The effects of price and health consciousness and satisfaction on the medical tourism experience,” *Journal of Healthcare Management*, vol. 62, no. 6, pp. 405–417, 2017, doi: 10.1097/JHM-D-16-00016.
- [67] J. Peng, X. Yang, S. Fu, and T. C. (T C.). Huan, “Exploring the influence of tourists’ happiness on revisit intention in the context of Traditional Chinese Medicine cultural tourism,” *Tourism Management*, vol. 94, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.tourman.2022.104647.
- [68] S. Yun and T. Kim, “Can nature-based solutions (NBSs) for stress recovery in green hotels affect re-patronage intention?,” *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 14, no. 6, 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14063670.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Suliyanto is a Full Professor of Marketing at Economics and Business Faculty, Jenderal Soedirman University (Unsoed). He is currently active at the Research Center Economics and Business Faculty, Unsoed and at research consulting institutions. He has published many articles in reputable national journals and reputable international journals indexed in Scopus and WoS. His research topics are mostly on Tourism marketing and Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). He has written books Business Research Methods, Applied Econometrics, Data Analysis in Marketing Applications. He can be contacted at email: suliyanto@unsoed.ac.id.

Rahab is an associate professor in marketing at the Faculty of Economics and Business at Jenderal Soedirman University, with a research focus on marketing and tourism. He is also active in the research center for rural resource development. He has extensive research experience in formulating policies in collaboration with local governments. He can be contacted at email: rahab@unsoed.ac.id.

Destia Vindha Arini is a research assistant at the Research Center of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Jenderal Soedirman University, with a research focus on Marketing. She is also active in the entrepreneurship club. With prior experiences as an intern in digital marketing, she is well-prepared to take on the challenges of the marketing industry and aspires to work in the FMCG Industry. She can be contacted at email: destia.arini@mhs.unsoed.ac.id.